

Energy Rating Systems for Green Building (Focus on Improved Awareness of Professionals)

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ABSTRACT

A sustainable design optimises resources, restores and renews them; and provides an aesthetic that contributes in a positive manner, both now and in the future. The drive towards creating sustainable cities and neighbourhoods have climaxed in recent years; owing to the painful realisation of the deplorable worldwide energy crunch. Following this, there has been a plethora of scholarly recommendations and practical tactics, employed or at least advocated for, by concerned organisations, associations and even governments in a bid to control the depletion of Mother Nature's resources. Several such bodies undertake certification exercises on new and existing buildings and generate energy rating techniques which helps promote and publicise the need for energy conservation in buildings and also invariably attracts clients to such buildings while raising its socio-economic value. It is however regrettable, that amidst such rigorous campaign for more-environmental friendly construction and energy saving technology, one would shudder to find that most professionals; even among the so called 'elite' of the society, possess a less than acceptable amount of knowledge regarding the supposed means of making a building sustainable and its measurement criteria.

The aim of this paper is to intimate the relevant professionals on the various energy rating standards that obtain in the building circle today such as LEED, BREEAM, HK-BEAM, GREEN STAR, etc. We review them in context with the civilisations where they are found along with the requirements for obtaining such certifications. The author's view is that knowledge of these standards would foster critical response to the environmental issues of energy dissipation and natural resource depletion.

Keywords— energy saving, energy rating system, measurement criteria, certification.

1. INTRODUCTION

Man has been found on the earth for thousand of years. Archeologers say that he is among the oldest surviving species of animal life here. These years has been long years of living, planting, building, and reproducing. His morphology has even been said to transform, dating back to the Stone Age man and supported by the Lamarck's theory of evolution which holds that species do change over time. And he has seen series of civilisations from the Iron Age through, to the information age.

For all these time, he has been the chief manipulator of his immediate environment the roots of which can be traced to the biblical instance where God created man and empowered him to 'dominate and subdue' the earth. From which time he has continued to learn and improve his conditions of living harnessing the naturally endowed 'earth'.

Today, the world's natural resources are getting usurped at an alarming rate and the environment which we live and work in bears the creul brunt of man's activities daily on such huge amounts that even the skin of our atmosphere is affected.

Scientists and researchers have however come to this realisation and Most are conversant with the rigorous campaigns going on in every sector, and industry regarding means of arresting this nightmare. Among these are seminars, lectures, building codes and regulations, construction standards etc which aim at enlightening the professionals on how best to tackle the issues of sustainability and energy conservation. These standards have been well developed into organised energy rating systems that enable owners-including home owners, corporations, government entities and developers evaluate their investment while aiding designers and constructors set targets.

Sadly at first, these rating systems, did not receive the much clamoured attention by building owners who perceived it as an unnecessary and unrecoverable cost. But this view has changed in the last few decades largely owing to the increased concerns about climate change and interest in sustainable design. They now view them as measures, guides, marketing tools and a way to lower long run operating costs of new and existing buildings.

It is not the author's intent, to remind us of what we know already in that we need to fit into this relentless campaign for green building solutions, but rather we shall review the criteria that qualifies a building to be termed 'green' in the first place and the 'metric' upon which it is measured.

We commence by taking a look at the elements of a green building, and the need for energy rating systems, (from here onwards occasionally referred to as ENRS,) then we shall outline the various energy rating systems that apply in various societies and disciplines along with brief explanation of their requirements for eligibility and implementation proceeedure, a brief schematic comparism shall be drawn and recommendations shall be proffered on how we can effectively choose a rating system to apply. Further recommendations on awareness creation to salvage the heartmelting illiteracy of professionals-especially Architects, from the previous construction era who have failed to identify with the energy-conservation epoch; will be given.

2. ELEMENTS OF A GREEN BUILDING

Clients, often want an environmentally-friendly building but do not fully understand what it entails or even costs. Thus professionals commissioned to design and erect sustainable buildings may have to first intimate their clients on what is expected of a green building and invariably assist them in setting their goals before getting on with the project.

According to the United states Environmental Protection Agency (EPA),

Green building is the practice of creating structures and using processes that are environmentally responsible and resource-efficient throughout a building's life-cycle from siting to design, construction, operation, maintenance, renovation and deconstruction.

Thus a green house or a sustainable building is a structure that is designed to take advantage of presently existing resources around it to create an aesthetic and functional living space which serves today's need and is relatively cheaper to maintain in the long run.

[Fig. 1: A rendering of a fully equipped net zero structure. (Josh Englander: square footage)]

According to Ar. C.Pradeepa, in her paper titled: 'Green Building-the quest for sustainability' which was published in the Proceedings of the National Conference on Sustainable Architecture and Green Buildings, 2008; The elements that make up a green building include;

2.1 Siting

The building site should be well situated to take advantage of the transportation routes while the building is carefully oriented to take maximum advantage of the sun at most times of the day and the site well landscaped with water conserving plants.

2.2 Energy Efficiency

The design must employ such measures as passive solar design, and the ample use of natural lighting to reduce building energy consumption.

2.3 Material Efficiency

Use of durable locally sourced materials, Reuse of recycled materials, use of materials that have low off gassing of harmful air and low toxicity, and use of insulating materials to maintain a favourable interior condition.

2.4 Water Efficiency

The design must have techniques for water conservation and re-use of recycled water and alternative means of supply which reach the house for use within a reasonable time interval.

2.5 Health and Safety Of Users

The occupants' health and safety regarding internal thermal conditions and fire, respectively, must be provided for.

2.6 Efficient Maintenance System

Well scheduled and implemented maintenance exercise on the building must be provided for to ensure the building remains functionally energy efficient as designed.

If we accept these elements as the requirements for a green building, then we must have a basis to justify how much 'green' or 'not green' a building is relative to another; which brings us to the need for energy rating systems.

3. WHY DO WE NEED ENERGY RATING SYSTEMS?

An energy rating system is a standardised means of evaluating a building's energy efficiency and expected energy costs. It is localised to different societies and disciplines but are sometimes used complementarily. It is usually formulated by approved bodies such as state building development boards, environmental protection agencies or non-profit bodies etc who specify the required standards and carry out evaluation and certification exercises on new and existing building constructions.

There is a difference in the need for energy efficient buildings and the need for techniques for rating or measuring energy efficiency of a building though both are complementary needs. Less emphasis on the former as we are conversant with that, but it would do us some good if we mentioned a few of the benefits here, to explain the need for a system or systems of measurement.

First, there are environmental benefits, which include elimination of toxic substances and therefore reduced impact on human health, reduction of waste, and effluent emissions to the environment leading to a cleaner and more habitable surrounding. Second, the economic benefits; which includes long term cost savings and increase in property demand due to acclaimed energy saving values of the building. Then there are social benefits also like improved living conditions for the community and accommodation of physically challenged persons.

These benefits are the major drive for demand in the construction field today, and that explains the reason why clients and corporate bodies are increasingly subscribing to energy-efficient developments. It becomes imperative therefore, to generate a certain code or measurement scale for ascertaining a building's degree of 'greenness' which invariably affects its market value as well as socio-environmental importance, as we saw earlier.

4. ENERGY RATING SYSTEMS

In 1990, the UK established the first building assessment system, (BREEAM) after which other Countries adapted or created their own energy rating systems, responsive to their climates and cultural values. In some cases, a designer might get a project certified by a rating system which is designed for use in a different country because he is more conversant with that one or even because he thinks that particular system carries a greater market cache in the given locality. Foreign Rating Systems which are not indigenous to a given country or region are sometimes required to obtain an operation license in the country where it seeks to operate; for example the Canadian, Green Globes was required to acquire a license to promote and develop Green Globes in the United States in 2004.

Whatever the case or country, it is expedient that a reasonable understanding of the system is possessed by the design and construction professionals.

Some common ENRS that obtain today include; ENERGY STAR(United States), LEED(United States), BREEAM(UK), THREE STAR(China), CASBEE(Japan), Green Globes(Canada), Green Star(Australia), HK-BEAM(Hong Kong), CASBEE(Japan), Estidama's Pearl RS(Abu Dhabi), SBTool/iiSBE(Canada) etc.

For the purpose of this paper, we shall discuss three main ENRS which have been selected on basis of their International scope and acceptance in the construction industry; these are LEED, BREEAM and HK-BEAM which represent the American, UK and Hong Kong construction industries respectively.

4.1 LEED (leadership in Energy in Environmental Design)

LEED certification is a recognition that a construction project or building can attain by utilizing environmentally friendly building practices during construction or remodeling. It was developed by the U.S. Green Building Council in 1998 to encourage environmental awareness amongst government agencies, Clients and professionals.

4.1.1 LEED Rating

LEED certification can be attained on four different levels, which are determined by a credit, or point, system. The levels of LEED certification are;

- Certified (40-49 points).
- Silver (50-59 points).
- Gold (60-79 points).
- Platinum (80-above).

Up to 110 points may be earned in 7 different categories;

- Sustainable sites.
- Water efficiency.
- Energy and atmosphere.
- Materials and resources.
- Indoor environmental quality
- Innovation in design
- Regional priority.

In order to increase the number of new and redeveloped buildings eligible for LEED certification, the government also offers many incentives within the building industry, including grant funding and tax breaks based on the level of LEED certification attained.

Over the years the rating system has been updated often to accommodate new practices and building types. Presently certifications provided for include;

- LEED-New Construction.
- LEED for existing buildings: Operations and Maintenance.
- LEED for Commercial Interiors.

- LEED for Core and Shell.
- LEED for Retail.
- LEED for Healthcare.
- LEED for Homes.
- LEED for Neighbourhood Development.

4.1.2 The Procedure

A building or project can attain LEED certification by submitting an application that documents its compliance with the requirements set for in the LEED rating system. The Green Building Council issues LEED certification upon satisfactory application, review and compliance verification. However there are fees associated with LEED certification.

An overview of the process of obtaining a LEED certification;

1. Verify that your building is eligible for obtaining a LEED certification in the first instance. Information on eligibility criteria is provided in the LEED certification website.
2. Get the project registered online and pay the applicable fees.
3. Choose which rating system is most appropriate for your building type and fill out all necessary data in the online questionnaire provided through the project duration.
4. Upon project completion, submit it for review and certification.
5. Commit to providing whole building energy and water usage data to the GBCI (green building certification institute) and the USGBC (US green building council) for at least the first 5 years of occupancy.
6. Third party verification which involves an on-site inspection to confirm acclaimed energy standards usually performed by an independent consultant.

4.1.3 CASE STUDY 1; Hearst Tower, Manhattan- 'Gold certification'

Hearst Tower in Midtown Manhattan has achieved official "green" status--the first office building in New York City to be recognized by the USGBC for high environmental performance both on its exterior (core and shell) and interior fit-out and systems.

[Fig. 2 - Hearst Tower, Manhattan (source: www.tinygreenbubble.com)]

4.2 BREEAM (BRE Environmental Assessment Method).

The BREEAM rating system was launched in the UK in 1990, since then more than 199,000 developments have been certified thus making it the most widely used rating system in the world. It is administered by the Building Research Establishment(BRE) and its operation is accredited under (ISO)9001.

It has assessment systems for such building types as;

- Offices
- Courts
- Ecohomes
- industries
- Healthcare
- Prisons
- Retail
- Education

BREEAM offers Certifications for new buildings and existing buildings (BREEAM In-Use). BREEAM also offers certification to projects outside the UK. There is an international BREEAM option whereby a project team could send project details for BRE to prepare a proposal outlining the fee and time frame for a tailored BREEAM suite for the particular building type and location. This is usually done on demand only.

Assessment is based on the following categories;

- Management
- Health and wellbeing
- Energy
- Transport
- Water materials
- Land use and Ecology
- Pollution

4.2.1 BREEAM Rating

The total number of points or credits gained in each section is multiplied by an environmental weighting factor which takes into account the relative importance of each section. Section scores are then added together to produce a single overall score. Once the overall score for the building is known, this is translated into a rating on a scale of:

- Pass
- Good
- Very good
- Excellent
- Outstanding
- A star rating from 1 to 5 stars is also provided: *****

4.2.2 The Procedure

Assessments are carried out by independent Auditors who are trained and licensed by BRE Global. The Assessor produces a report outlining the development's performance in each of the sections and overall score. Upon completion of the assessment, the client is presented with a certificate confirming the BREEAM rating on BRE Global's behalf which highlight how well a building and organisation are performing and ways to improve.

The earlier an Assessor is involved in the design process, the easier it is to gain a high rating in the most of cost effective way.

4.2.3 CASE STUDY 2; Lion House, Alnwick, Northumberland, UK

The Lion House project in Alnwick, is a flagship ultra low emissions office designed to achieve exemplary standards of sustainability and environmental performance. IT is the first office ever to achieve BREEAM 'Outstanding' at Post Construction Review under the BREEAM 2008 offices category. Frank Shaw Associates was the appointed Architect and Lead Design Consultant acting for the Main Contractor, Kier North East. During construction the contractor confirmed that 91.48% of waste from the project was recycled, and its three wind turbines, biomass boiler, solar collectors and PV panels are predicted to save an incredible 48,000kg of CO2 every year.

[Fig. 3 - Lion House, Alnwick (Source: copyright frank shaw associates limited 2012)]

This means it has far exceeded current building regulations and has constructed an office block which is highly efficient, comfortable for building users and has a low environmental impact. For this reason Lion House has received the OGC Special Award for Government Sector Achievement in 2010 and won the BREEAM Awards 2008 for the Offices category.

4.3 HK-BEAM (Hong Kong Building Environmental Assessment Method)

The HK-BEAM was developed with BREEAM as a reference point and was first launched in 1996. By early 2009 there were 170 certified buildings, totalling 77 million square feet in Hong Kong and mainland China.

Two standards have been developed to appraise the environmental performance of Buildings at distinctive life cycle stages:

- HK-BEAM for New Building Developments.
- HK-BEAM for Existing building premises.

HK-BEAM covers environmental issues under the following impact categories at each stage of the building's life cycle

- Site Aspects (location, planning and emissions)
- Material aspects (selection, usage and waste management)
- Energy use (system designs and management)
- Water consumption (quality and conservation)
- Indoor environmental quality (thermal comfort, indoor air quality, lighting, noise and vibrations).
- Innovations (innovative techniques and performance enhancements).

4.3.1 HK-BEAM Rating

HK-BEAM assesses the entire building process from planning to construction to management and operation. Four levels of certification may be achieved with minimum requirements for the overall score and Indoor Environmental quality (IEQ) score. The levels are;

- Bronze (above average-40% overall, 40% IEQ)
- Silver (good- 55% overall, 50% IEQ)
- Gold (very good- 65% overall, 55% IEQ)
- Platinum (excellent- 75% overall, 65% IEQ)

4.3.2 The Procedure

An overview of the process of obtaining HK-BEAM certification;

7. The client approaches an approved assessor and indicates interest for the certification of a chosen building(s).
8. He completes the assessment checklists to provide the required project information.
9. The Assessor appraises the building against HK-BEAM best practice criteria via Computer simulations using HTB2/BECON, predicts energy and thermal performance.
10. Results are presented in the provisional assessment report, which identifies which credits have been achieved and how to improve performance.
11. Clients Pursues additional credits through refinements in building design, specification and management, submitting details for reassessment free of charge.
12. Assessor Evaluates the proposed improvements and undertakes construction site visits to verify adoption of the Agreed standards. The final assessment report and HK-BEAM certificate is issued

upon building completion to confirm overall environmental performance as a rating of Bronze, Silver, Gold, Platinum.

4.3.3 CASE STUDY 3; Bank Of China, Hong Kong

Bank of China (BOC) Tower was constructed over a period of four years and four months commencing in April 1985. Completed for occupancy in August 1989, the building was opened in May 1990, towering 70 floors above the ground floor level and offering parking in four basement levels. The tower structure of 315 metres and two masts of 50 odd metres give the building its aspiring height of 367.4 metres – which, in 1989, made it the tallest in Hong Kong as well as the fifth by height in the world. It is still one of the tallest office buildings in Hong Kong.

[Fig. x - Bank of China Tower, Hong Kong (source: wikimedia commons)]

The BOC Tower has won many construction awards locally and globally including; 2002 "Excellent" Award of Hong Kong Building Environmental Assessment Method;

5. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

How well the certified and rated buildings compare with each other is of an interest to building designers and policy makers. The general characteristics of the three ENRS hereby studied are compared in the table below; which represents part of a research work carried out by W.L. Lee, J. Burnett using (Department of Building Services Engineering, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University), using 60 buildings with HK-BEAM certifications and as much information as were available for BREEAM and LEED.

Table 1: General Comparison.

Item	HK-BEAM	LEED	BREEAM
Assessment Method	Mixture of performance-based and feature specific criteria	Options of feature specific criteria and cost budget method	Mixture of performance-based and feature specific criteria
Simulation tool	HTB2 + BECON or approved equivalent	DOE-2 or BLAST or approved equivalent	No specific requirements, actual consumption figures may be used where available.
Scope of assessment	Annual energy use, Max. Electricity demand, Energy efficient design, Envelope performance.	Energy efficient design. Annual energy cost.	Annual CO2 emissions. Energy efficient design.
Max. credit level performance based criteria	Reduction of 57% in annual energy use over the baseline case	Reduction of 60% in annual energy cost over the budget	Zero emissions
Min. Credit level performance based criteria	120kwh/sq.m/yr.	Reduction of 15% in annual energy cost over the budget	160 kg CO2 / sq.m /yr
Baseline case/zero credit level	Compliance with the minimum requirements laid down by relevant laws or codes of practice	Compliance with ASHRAE/ IESNA 90.1-1999	Compliance with DETR (1998) good practice guides
Energy-related credits/points (%)	23	25	20

(Source: W.L. Lee, J. Burnett; *Building and Environment* 43 (2008) 1882–1891)

After carrying out statistical analysis of the available data, using the outline established in the table above, they arrived at the following conclusion;

13. The performance levels of the baseline buildings are comparable.
14. The simulation tools are both in compliance with ASHRAE Standard 140.
15. The market positions of the certified buildings are in the top 25%.

From these result we find that the three ENRS are favourably comparable and widely accepted in the construction field. yet there are many other ENRS in operation globally, so the question becomes, how do we choose the most suitable ENRS for a given Project?

5.1 Choosing A Suitable ENRS

The ENRS which are in use today are location and type specific. This means that they are developed taking into consideration the requirements applicable to the given locality where they would be operational and also the minimum functional requirements of the particular building type. In some cases however a given rating system could be used in a different region from the one which it was designed for provided the regions are similar in climate and /or environmental character. Also, The designer's familiarity with a given ENRS would invariably encourage his choice for that system.

Generally, the choice of an ENRS is determined by the following;

- The Project location.
- The nature of building/design i.e. home, school, industry, office or healthcare.
- Popularity of the ENRS i.e. how accepted it is in the given region.

- Ease of Registration and Evaluation processes ie how rigorous or stringent the procedure of certification is.
- Cost of the Registration process.

6. TOWARDS AN ENRS-LITERATE DESIGN TEAM

It is evident from the afore going, that the success of a green building project, depends largely on how learned the members of the building team, (mainly the Architect) are on the subject of energy rating systems.

It is necessary to ensure that the members of the design team are all professional practitioners with some degree of experience in green building. While this is ensured, the Architect would take his position as the head of the design team and should not fail to remind the team members of the conduct required of them.

An orientation exercise at the beginning of the construction project and occasionally as deemed fit by the Architect, would suffice to educate the members of the unskilled labour team on environmental best practices during the project life cycle.

The call therefore is for Architects in the new age practice to brace themselves with necessary knowledge of energy rating systems for green buildings as we have realised that the knowledge of the need for green building is not enough, one also needs to understand how that is achieved and measured.

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